

Review Article

Reflections on the Normative Power of the (Im)possible

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When medical sociologist Aaron Antonovsky analysed interviews with women going through menopause, he discovered something unexpected. Among the respondents were women who had survived the Nazi concentration camps. Surprisingly, about 29 percent of them were in relatively good physical and mental health [1].

Antonovsky's first thought was that this must be a miracle. But then he asked a different question. How was this possible? Could it be that health does not merely disappear—but can actually emerge, even under extremely adverse circumstances?

And if that is the case, another question arises: How exactly does health emerge?

This question became the starting point for what Antonovsky later termed salutogenesis. Instead of merely asking what causes illness, he asked:

How does health emerge?

Salutogenesis focuses on the resources that people mobilize in difficult situations, as well as on what Antonovsky called a sense of coherence—a fundamental orientation that helps people experience life as understandable, manageable, and meaningful.

In health research, situations in which people succeed despite difficult circumstances are often described as positive deviance [2]. Positive deviance refers to cases in which something works against all odds. Unexpected solutions emerge from within the system itself. This is also possible in everyday medical practice, even in situations that seem chronically deadlocked (Figure 1).

The initial situation might look like this: Doctor and patient sit across from each other for a routine consultation as part of the ongoing care of a chronic illness; both are looking at their records (computer or patient chart). In a sense, they live in different worlds. The

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desk between them symbolically separates these worlds. Each brings their own interpretation of the situation—their own explanations, expectations, and concerns. They must first, so to speak, lay these perspectives on the table before mutual understanding can emerge [3].

Figure 1: Separate worlds.

A contrasting scene (Figure 2): Here, the doctor and patient sit diagonally across from each other at the table. This slight spatial shift already suggests a first step toward interaction rather than confrontation. The patient suffers from chronic pain and has been seeing her doctor almost weekly for quite some time. Many attempts at treatment have already been made—without decisive success. Over time, the consultations had almost become a ritual. The parties involved remain friendly and respectful—but the situation has stagnated, and an unspoken dissatisfaction hangs in the air, along with the feeling that perhaps things could be different [4].

Figure 2: A chronic consultation.

The doctor uses a discussion of the findings during a routine health checkup as an opportunity for a fresh start and suggests attending a support group: this, he explains, is a chance to reflect together on the underlying causes and ways of managing her pain. The patient, however, reacts with fear—including fear of losing her primary care

physician. She responds with a very simple question: “And what happens if I just don’t go?”

This question becomes a major turning point. The doctor assures her that her decision will not affect their relationship. Their relationship remains stable. This promise creates a sense of security in their relationship, and on this basis, the conversation can take a new direction.

Together, they get to the root of her fear. They simulate the situation she imagines—entering a room full of strangers and talking about her experiences. It’s actually an everyday situation, and gradually the situation seems less threatening. And yet the patient still hesitates.

At this point, the doctor draws attention to his own limitations and makes an unusual request. “I can’t really understand your resistance, and it seems to me that I can’t reach you here. I’d like you to give the group a try. Could we try a different approach? How about if you follow my advice—as if I’d prescribed you a pill?” (Figure 3).

Figure 3: A small pact.

The patient can agree to this request. A small pact is formed between the doctor and the patient as person—sealed and concluded both physically and symbolically with a handshake. The patient agrees to try the support group. Not because she is completely convinced—but because she is willing to engage in this shared experiment. At that moment, the consultation shifts from a treatment to a collaboration.

Some time later, the patient reports that she has indeed been attending the group regularly. She hasn’t even spoken up herself there. Nevertheless, her situation improved significantly. She didn’t need surgery. She was able to stop taking her medication. Her doctor visits became much less frequent. Later, she described her experience vividly: “I needed a kick in the butt—because I had never learned to talk about health.”

A closer analysis of the conversation reveals something interesting. At first glance, the doctor appears to dominate the conversation. He speaks more and actively tries to find solutions. Yet the decisive

turning points are initiated by the patient—mostly through brief questions. Thus, it seems that the success of the conversation is based on more than the application of a therapeutic technique. Rather, both participants gradually grow beyond their prescribed roles. They begin to encounter one another not only as doctor and patient, but as human beings. They recognize both their resources and their limitations. And through this coordinated interplay, a moment of positive deviation emerges. A moment in which something becomes possible that previously seemed impossible.

Positive deviation therefore appears to be something paradoxical. It seems impossible—until it actually happens. And yet such possibilities may be latent in many interactions. Sometimes they come to light through a simple question. Sometimes through a moment of hesitation. Sometimes simply because someone waits long enough for a new perspective to open up. In such moments, stories about illness can gradually open up into stories about health.

The case outlined here points to something more general. Health can emerge in situations where people go beyond prescribed roles and begin to recognize one another as persons. If we take this idea seriously, it raises a further question:

How can our Healthcare Systems Become Places that Foster Such Encounters?

Perhaps this points to what the Ottawa Charter referred to as a “caring community” [5]—that is, a community based on care. Perhaps this is also why the physician Viktor von Weizsäcker once asked:

“How much longer will physicians and generals shape our view of the world instead of poets and artists [6]?”

For perhaps health arises precisely where people begin to perceive one another not merely as roles, but as persons [7].

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